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**60 YEARS OF NEW YORK CONVENTION ON RECOGNITION OF
ARBITRAL AWARDS. EXPERIENCE OF SPAIN**

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There are 60 years since the Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (known as New York Convention) has been signed. The present article offers a concise presentation of the New York Convention, focusing on the conceptual evolution of international commercial arbitration in Spain and its importance in the economic and cultural development of its society.

Keywords: *international arbitration; New York Convention; arbitration law; arbitration procedure; lis pendens.*

**60 DE ANI AI CONVENȚIEI DE LA NEW YORK PRIVIND RECUNOAȘTEREA PREMIILOR
ARBITRALE. EXPERIENȚA SPANIEI**

Sunt 60 de ani de la semnarea Convenției privind recunoașterea și executarea hotărârilor judecătorești arbitrale străine (cunoscută sub numele de Convenția de la New York). Articolul de față propune o prezentare concisă a Convenției de la New York, cu accentul pe evoluția conceptuală a arbitrajului comercial internațional din Spania și importanța acestuia în dezvoltarea economico-culturală a societății.

Cuvinte-cheie: *arbitraj internațional; Convenția de la New-York; legea arbitrajului; procedura de arbitraj; lis pendens.*

I. Introduction

In Spain, since the end of the last half century to the present day, we have been privileged witnesses of a notable cultural evolution in the field of arbitration as an alternative method of dispute resolution (ADR). In fact, of all the existing ADR methods, arbitration is nowadays the most known and used in our country, both by companies and by individuals.

According to recent data, arbitration is the alternative dispute resolution system most used by Spanish companies, in particular those operating in the international market.

II. Legislative background

But this has not always been the case. Spain has remained for many years oblivious to this phenomenon. Until the currently in force Law 60/2003, in Spain there had been only two laws on arbitra-

tion: Law of 22 December 1953, and Law 36/1988, of 5 of December (repealed by the current Law 60/2003).

There are strong differences among the three of them:

1. Law of 22 December 1953, on Arbitration of Private Law:

The Law of 1953 was highly criticized by the international and national legal doctrine, to the point of being known in Spain as „*the Antiarbitration Law*”.

The modern arbitral system in Spain took off, without any doubt, with the ratification of the widely known international conventions on international commercial arbitration (starting with the European Convention on International Commercial Arbitration, made at Geneva on 21 April 1961; In 1977, with the ratification of the Convention on the Recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral judgments, made in new York on 10 June 1958. And, after enormous political and diplomatic reticence, with the Washington Convention of 1965, that allowed Spain to have Access to the World Bank’s modern system of interstate arbitration in investment matters).

Although it is superfluous to say that the rules contained in international conventions are part of our domestic legal system (and therefore without directly applicable) or that its provisions can only be repealed, modified or suspended in the form envisaged in the treaties themselves, or in accordance with the general rules of international law, our Supreme Court has taken a long time to draw all the consequences that the conventional regime of international arbitration imposes on our country. Thus, it ignored the existence of the international conventions, mixed issues of the internal arbitral system with other derivatives of the specific international regulation, and applied the exemption of public or-

der in an undue and abusive way to refuse the recognition and enforcement of foreign awards...

Breaking inertia of decades, on February 11, 1981 the first Chamber of the Supreme Court drafted a resolution modifying the previous jurisprudential line of practically denying the exequatur to the foreign arbitral awards in Spain [1]. The facts of the case had to do with a charter contract signed between a Finnish and a Spanish company in which the parties included a clause according to which any dispute that arose before or during the execution of the charter would be settled in London by arbitration. Each party would appoint an arbitrator and, if they did not reach a uniform solution, a third arbitrator would be appointed in discord and his/her decision would be the final one. Similarly, the parties added that if any of them refused to designate the arbitrator, the appointee would have the right to decide on his/her own, being his/her decision binding for both of them. In this case, it was discussed whether the arbitral award intended to be executed in Spain was contrary to the public order based on the postulates of the Law of 1953. The answer was clear: if the content of the public order exemption is the content of the Law of 1953 on Private Arbitration (and therefore, applicable the exception of article 954 LEC), the provisions of the treaties on international arbitration would end up as empty provisions “... *since it would suffice to the Spanish merchant not to cooperate in the appointment of the arbitrators to avoid the future execution of the award*”. Consequently, from this judicial resolution of the Spanish Supreme Court, the Law of 1953 could not be wielded against a foreign award obtained abroad. It was the first step towards the incorporation of Spain into the mechanisms of international commercial arbitration. And, what is more important, this judicial resolution did not remain an isolated precedent, but was soon continued by most

than half a hundred decisions, insisting in the same doctrine. This resolution changed the jurisprudential line in Spain in a radical way around the acceptance of the exequatur of foreign arbitral award.

2. Law 36/1988 of 5 of December, on Arbitration:

Law of 1988 was generally considered in a very positive way. However, after the years and the new circumstances of the market, Law 36/1988 became soon outdated and several gaps and technical imperfections were manifested in particular in its international dimension [2].

III. Law 60/2003, on arbitration

These previous arguments linked to the needs of improvement and monitoring the evolution of arbitration, together with the desirability of accommodating the Spanish system to the UNCITRAL Model Law on International arbitration, in line with the other contemporary arbitral systems, served the Spanish legislator to justify the need of reform and the subsequent promulgation of the current Spanish Law 60/2003, on Arbitration.

Spain is a clear example of how legislative measures have been essential in the evolution of arbitration. The approval (on December 26, 2003), and subsequent entry into force (on March 26, 2004) of Law 60/2003 has had a direct effect on how, in a relatively short time, Spain has moved from a strong distrust towards arbitral Justice (or even from its frontal rejection as an alternative dispute resolution method), to recognize arbitration as the most appropriate instrument of justice for settling disputes. And, even more, to prevent and reduce the workload of the ordinary courts. This law is characterized by the following notes:

1. *Pre-eminence of the will of the parties and flexibility:* The will of the parties underlies the whole arbitral legal system, spreading its effect to issues such as the procedure for the designation

of arbitrators, the rules on which they will act, the determination of the place of arbitration, the language... The only limits to the will of parties are the principles of equality, hearing and contradiction.

2. *It adopts the monist model:* The law designs a single regime for both, internal and international arbitration, without almost no differences among them except for a few provisions.

3. *Modernization and avant-garde:* It allows the use of telematics means in the litigation procedures. The arbitration agreement and the award may be recorded in electronic, optical or other support. It is also admitted that communications are made through instruments such as telex, fax, or other means of electronic or telematics communication that allow the sending and receipt of writings or documents.

4. *It is based on the minimum intervention of the judicial courts:* the Law clearly lists the situations in which judges can act (as for as when their assistance is required for the taking of evidence, or for controlling the procedure of annulment of the award or its exequatur). So, the legislator makes clear the autonomous life of arbitration and the framework of collaboration with judges and courts (reduced to the essential minimum).

5. *Primacy of arbitration of Law over Equity:* Arbitration on equity will only be effected when expressly agreed by the parties. If nothing is said about it, the dispute will be solved on Law.

6. *It empowers institutional arbitration:* Law 60/2003 enumerates the entities to which the administration of the arbitration can be entrusted.

7. *It improves the regulation of the principle Kompetenz-Kompetenz:* This principle allows arbitrators to decide on their own faculties or even on the validity of the arbitration agreement. This principle is in line with the autonomy of the arbitral agreement, as a separate and independent part of the main contract.

IV. The enforcement of foreign arbitral awards

IV.1. Competent judicial court:

In relation to the jurisdictional bodies responsible for the enforcement of foreign arbitral awards, New York Convention has enjoyed three different moments in its application in Spain. Until the beginning of the 21st century, with the approval of the Law 60/2003 and the subsequent reform of the Spanish Procedural Law (LEC) of 1881, the responsible court for the recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards was the Supreme Court.

As of the reform of 2003, this competence was transferred to the first instance (or commercial courts, depending on the matters covered by the award). The change of the objective competence had as a consequence to facilitate to the maximum the recognition and enforcement of foreign awards, to the extent that the same court responsible for the recognition is the same as the court responsible for the subsequent execution. The change however generated as a negative consequence the difficulty of verifying the Spanish case Law in the matter (something easy when the court objectively competent for recognition was the Supreme Court).

The situation is again amended in 2011 (following the adoption of Law 11/2011 of 20 May), attributing competition for the recognition of international arbitral awards to the Civil and Criminal Chamber of the Superior Court of Justice of the Autonomous Community of: 1º) the domicile or place of residence of the party against who the recognition is requested; or 2º) of the domicile or place of residence of the person to whom the effects refers to; or 3º) the territorial jurisdiction will be subsidiary determined by the place of execution or where those arbitral awards must produce their effects. If requested by the parties, once the recognition is

obtained, the execution shall belong to the First Instance Court in accordance with the same criteria.

IV.2. Procedure:

Article 46 of the Spanish Arbitration Act states that the exequatur of foreign arbitral awards “*shall be substantiated in accordance with the procedure laid down in the civil procedural order for judgments dictated by foreign courts*”.

The procedure is the of articles 52-55 of International Legal Cooperation in Civil Matters Act (ILCCMA). The term to enter an appearance will be that of thirty days. After that term, the court will continue knowing about the case, even if it has not appeared the aforementioned [3].

The Supreme Court has applied these procedural provisions emphasizing that the important thing is the right of the parties to effective judicial protection, granted by article 24 of the Spanish Constitution [4].

To obtain the exequatur, it is necessary to present the documents provided for in article IV of the New York Convention of 1958. That is, (i) The duly authenticated original award or a duly certified copy thereof; (ii) The original arbitration agreement or a duly certified copy thereof. The applicant may, of course, present any other documents which he considers necessary (as for, the notifications made to the party in absentia) [5].

Even if the Law does not expressly say so, the Supreme Court has always granted the actor a remission of the statement of opposition to the exequatur filed by the defendant [6].

IV.3. Grounds for refusal: a practical perspective:

Article 46.2 of the Arbitration Act stipulates that “*The exequatur of foreign arbitral awards shall be governed by the Convention on the Recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral judgments, made in new York, on 10 June 1958, without prejudice to the*

provisions of other International conventions more favorable to it". Articles IV and V of the said Convention, which are generally applied by the Spanish judge to decide on the exequatur, are therefore of great importance.

Obviously, there is no way in the exequatur procedure to allege the lack of conformity with the decision taken [7]. The nationality of the award does not matter, unless the exequatur is based on a treaty other than the New York Convention of 1958 (Spain has not made any reservation in this respect when this Convention was ratified) [8]. Moreover, foreign procedural problems cannot be invoked if they have not caused defenselessness [9]. On the following pages the judicial application of the causes of denial of the exequatur will be analyzed, following the exhaustive research made by CREMADES SANZ-PASTOR [10]:

IV.3.1. Public Order exception:

In international matters, the scope of the public order exception is very limited and has to be interpreted in a restrictive manner. In the Judicial Order of March 4, 2003 the Supreme Court defined the notion of international public order: *„The exequatur procedure has a purely homologous nature which prevents, above all, the examination of the substance of the matter, without any other exception than that which represents the safeguarding of the public order of the Forum. The Constitutional Court has specified that the concept of public order of the Forum, as a limit to the recognition and enforcement of foreign resolution, has acquired a new dimension since the entry into force of the Spanish Constitution of 1978, in which, without discussion, penetrates the set of principles that inspire our constitutional order and among them, especially, the fundamental rights and public liberties, acquiring a peculiar content impregnated by the requirements imposed by art. 24 so that, at the international le-*

vel, such a concept is essentially identified with the constitutionally enshrined rights and guarantees in relation to the prohibition of the defencelessness imposed by article 24.2 of the Spanish Constitution. This defencelessness is to be material, real and effective, not merely formal, being only relevant the fact that on party is deprived unreasonably of the opportunity to defend his procedural position, suffering an effective impairment of its rights and interests, integrating the interpretation of the Constitutional Court, by the one carried out by the European Court of Human Rights" [11].

However, it should be clarified the scope of this assertion according to which the concept of public order at international level *"is essentially identified with the constitutionally enshrined rights and guarantees in connection with the prohibition of Defenselessness"*. In procedural terms it is certainly so. But it should not be forgotten that, although very exceptional, there are other demands of the public order much more restrictive, as for example, the existence of a Spanish decision with the value of *res iudicata*.

IV.3.2. Lack of a valid arbitration agreement:

The Supreme Court will also deny the exequatur of the award when the existence of an agreement to submit a dispute to arbitration is not proven. For example, the recognition of an award has been rejected in a case in which the requesting party failed to provide the document where the arbitration agreement is collected in the manner described in Article II.2 of the New York Convention (the claimant only provided a copy of a the sales contract in which although there was a clause relating to GAFTA trade rules No. 125, but it did not appear signed by the defendant, but only by the plaintiffs) [12].

According to the case Law of the Spanish Supreme Court, there is no need, for any specific formula to confirm the intention of the parties to

be submitted to arbitration. So, for example, the Supreme Court granted the exequatur to an award of the International Arbitral Tribunal of Strasbourg despite the absence of the written arbitration agreement, because it was considered that the appearance before the arbitrator without making any reservation was equivalent to signing an arbitration agreement [13]. With the same flexible criteria, the Supreme Court granted the exequatur despite the fact that the firm condemned in the award repeatedly affirmed the inexistence of the arbitration clause, since one of the two confirmations on whose back they appeared was not signed by her (*“Doubts arise, therefore, regarding this second document. Now, of the group of those who have contributed to the process, and who reflect the exchange of communications between the parties - through the intermediary, on occasion - for the celebration and execution of the successive agreements on the supply of goods, it can reasonably be inferred their willingness to submit the disputes arising in the development of business relations to the judgment of arbitrators”*) [14]. Not to forget the important Judgment of February 6, 2003, in which the Supreme Court stated that *“the clause of submission expressed by consent of the insured is opposable to the insurer that, in accordance with art. 780 of the Commercial Code, is subrogated in its place by virtue of the payment”* [15].

IV.3.3. Non-participation in the arbitration procedure:

To be in default has to be involuntary and must be cause of defenselessness. Under no other circumstances the non-participation in the arbitration procedure may constitute a cause of denial of the enforcement of the award. For example, An Order of the Supreme Court of April 27, 1999 [16] granted the exequatur to an award rendered in Rotterdam. The defendant alleged the breach of the rights of defense, such as the lack of citation and summons

in the arbitration proceedings. The Supreme Court established that, although the communications of the arbitration institution were serviced by ordinary mail, there were certifications of the Dutch postal employees and of the Spanish ones.

IV.3.4. Irregularities in the arbitration procedure:

By Judicial Order of October 7, 2003, the Supreme Court granted the exequatur to an award issued by the Commission of International Economic and Trade Arbitration of China, despite the defendant alleged the exception of public order in the development of the arbitration procedure: *“The verification of the alleged lack of impartiality, such as the verification of the breach of the public order in which it may be included, must be verified in casu, verifying the truth and effectiveness of the objective and subjective impartiality required of Members of the decision-making bodies of controversies within a democratic society”*. The Spanish company was also condemned in its arbitration in Chinese language but the Supreme Court stated that it cannot be appreciated defenselessness because of the development of the procedure in Chinese language when the Spanish company has habitual commercial relationships in the State of that language [17].

The Supreme Court granted a book to an award rendered in London by the GAFTA Arbitral Tribunal, International Association for the Trade in Feed and Grain, despite the fact that the opponent invoked that the procedure was not the one designed by the parties, because the support of a lawyer was not allowed for one of the parties. The Supreme Court rejects this argument stating that this argument had already been alleged in the arbitration procedure itself and that it was rejected by the Court [18].

IV.3.5. Lis pendens in Spain:

The pendency in Spain of a procedure whose decision could be incompatible with the effects of the

foreign resolution that is to be executed is another cause of denial of the enforcement of the arbitral award.

By Judicial Order of June 20, 2000 the Supreme Court denied the exequatur on *lis pendens* in Spain to an award issued by a Court appointed by the International Chamber of Commerce, since *“The characterization of the concept of lis pendens in the specific field of recognition and enforcement of foreign decisions, more specific if it is possible that the international lis pendens - the impediment of the decision of the lawsuit promoted in the forum -, is based on the need to avoid the concurrence, even possible, of two resolutions that in themselves or by their effects they are impossible to coexist, a condition that does not require, in principle, an identity of parties and an absolute coincidence of objects and causes must mediate, or that the pending process in Spain has necessarily begun before the one promoted abroad or the request for recognition of the resolution that terminated it”* [19].

Another example is the Judicial Order of the Supreme Court of September 24, 2002 [20]. An Italian company (MARE BLU SOCIETA DI NAVIGAZIONE ARL) applied for the exequatur of the arbitration award of December 3, 1999, issued by the arbitrator D. Bruce H. in London. This arbitration award condemned the Spanish company HARI-NAS DEL GUADALQUIVIR, S.L. to pay a certain amount of money. The Spanish company opposed the exequatur alleging the existence of another proceeding pending in Spain. The Supreme Court knows that the New York Convention of 1958 does not admit the *lis pendens* as a cause of denial of the enforcement, but links the *lis pendens* notion to the vague concept of public order whenever the Spanish proceeding is instituted before the foreign arbitral procedure. This could be an important risk because it entails to translate into the field of the en-

forcement of arbitral awards the model of the Spanish procedural Law of 1881 [21].

IV.3.6. Opening of a bankruptcy proceeding in Spain:

On different occasions, the Supreme Court has ruled on the incidence of the opening of a collective procedure in Spain over the enforcement of a foreign Award. Today this problem is expressly regulated by Bankruptcy Law 22/2003, of July 9 [22], which provides that the arbitration agreements will be without effect during the competition but that the arbitration proceedings in process will be followed until the firmness of the award (44).

V. Conclusions:

The grounds upon which recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards may be denied have been generally rejected by the Spanish jurisdictional bodies in direct, correct and coherent application of the New York Convention of 1958 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (which establishes a closed set of criteria for rejecting the recognition of foreign arbitral awards in its jurisdiction).

However, this almost unidirectional practice has not prevented the existence of some wrong resolutions. Among the reasons for refusal that have been accepted by some of our courts we must highlight two of them:

a) The wrongful interpretation of the public order exemption: The importance of the question raised is evident by observing the reasons that tend to be incardinated within the generic notion of “public order”. It is thus spoken: (i) Of lack of notification to the parties and, therefore, the impossibility of answering the claim; (ii) Of the absence of translation of certain documents from English to Spanish; (iii) Of the language used in the arbitration; (iv) Of the absence of necessary passive joinder of defendants; (v) Of the no notification of

the appointment of the arbitrators; (vi) Of the absence of motivation; (vii) Of the violation of the procedural principles of equality and contradiction [23]...

b) The growing remission to the *litis pendens* between the arbitration procedure developed abroad and the pending proceeding before the Spanish courts, as a cause for the refusal of recognition.

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2. Regarding the evolution of International Commercial Arbitration in Spain between 1953 and 1988, *vid.* Fernández Rozas, J.C.: „La situación actual de arbitraje comercial en España: perspectivas de futuro”, *Revista de la Corte Española de Arbitraje*, vol. III, 1986, pp. 29- 52.
3. Art. 54.5 ILCCMA.
4. For example, in a Judicial Order of March 4, 2003 closed and exequatur proceeding of and arbitral award laid down by the European Court of Arbitration of Versailles because the plaintiff's attorney notified that she was definitively retired in the exercise of her profession. The Supreme Court required the lawyer of the claimant so that within 20 days he would appear to be represented by a new procurator. And not having attended the request, had re-impacted a new period of 20 days. After expired, the Supreme ordered the file of the procedure (ATS 2454/2003 - ECLI:ES:TS:2003:2454A).
5. For example, by Judicial Order of March 4, 2003, the Supreme Court rejected the opposition to an Exequatur based on the fact that the rules of the arbitral institution had not been provided, because this document is not envisaged in the Convention (ATS 2447/2003 - ECLI:ES:TS:2003:2447A).
6. Although by Judicial Order of October 7, 2003, the Supreme Court pointed out that that such remission cannot be used for the claimant to present documentation that should have been delivered with the request for exequatur (ATS 10137/2003 - ECLI:ES:TS:2003:10137A).
7. The Judicial Order of the Supreme Court of 29 September 1998, granted the Exequatur to an award from the Paris Arbitral Chamber between a Moroccan company and a Spanish one, despite the fact that it was alleged the „*incoherence of the arbitral award*” (ATS 1436/1998 - ECLI:ES:TS:1998:1436A).
8. Judicial Order of Supreme Court of May 31, 2005 (ATS 6700/2005 - ECLI:ES:TS:2005:6700A).
9. The Judicial Order of the Supreme Court of June 9, 1998 which grants the exequatur to three English awards. The Supreme Court rejected the exception of necessary passive joinder of defendants invoked by the opponent. The argument used by the Supreme Court was that the defendant had opportunity to invoke this argument before the Arbitrators (ATS 394/1998 - ECLI:ES:TS:1998:394A).
10. „El exequátur de laudos extranjeros”, *Diario La Ley* (15944/2008).
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12. Judicial Order of May 4, 1999 (ATS 949/1999 - ECLI:ES:TS:1999:949A)
13. By order of March 31, 1998 (ATS 183/1998 - ECLI:ES:TS:1998:183A),
14. Judicial order of November 13, 2002 (ATS 2115/2001 - ECLI:ES:TS:2001:2115A)
15. STS 713/2003 - ECLI:ES:TS:2003:713.
16. ATS 1214/1999 - ECLI:ES:TS:1999:1214A. In the same sense, Judicial Order the Supreme Court of March 13, 2001 (ATS 773/2001 - ECLI:ES:TS:2001:773A), or of December 7, 2005 (ATS 17949/2005 - ECLI:ES:TS:2005:17949A)
17. ATS 10137/2003 - ECLI:ES:TS:2003:10137A.
18. Judicial Order of the Supreme Court of May 5, 1998 (ATS 2244/1998 - ECLI:ES:TS:1998:2244A),
19. Judicial Oder of the Supreme Court of April, 27, 1999 (ATS 1214/1999 - ECLI:ES:TS:1999:1214A). In this case, the applicant of the exequatur had obtained an award declaring the responsibility for the tax debts of the acquired company on the basis of the guarantee granted in the purchase and sale of the shares. The opponents of the exequatur had filed a lawsuit before the Court of First Instance of Zamora requesting the nullity of the contracts of sale. The Supreme Court said: „*It is observed, therefore, that even when there is no absolute identity between the subjects, object and cause of both procedures, the interrelation between them is undeniable. Thus, the obvious reasons for legal security, necessarily tied to the matter of*

recognition that is now examined, advise the denial of the exequatur as long as the procedure followed in the forum is not resolved, and without prejudice to the effects that the possible sentence could have". However, it must be emphasized that the Supreme Court based its decision on the chronology of both procedures, stating that the Spanish procedure was initiated before the arbitration.

On the contrary, by Judicial Order of 20 March 2001 (ATS 695/2001 - ECLI:ES:TS:2001:695A), the Supreme Court granted the exequatur to an award issued by the Arbitral Tribunal of the Waren-Verein der Haburger Börse of Hamburg, despite the fact that the defendants had initiated a procedure in Spain requesting the declaration of nullity of the clause of submission to arbitration. The arbitration procedure was initiated before the Spanish one, and the Supreme Court considered that tribunals should act *"with the aim always in the avoidance of fraudulent and claudicans situations, because otherwise would encourage and give a letter of nature to the procedural fraud protecting conducts contrary to the good faith and*

elusive of the duties and commitments freely assumed by the parties".

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